

Supplemental Material

Table S1 Environmental predictors used to represent inland wetland conditions which were summarised into one annual average in each of 30 years from 1982 to 2011 at both a continental spatial scale and regional (within 500 km) scale.

Variable	Description	Source	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution
Predicted inland abundance	modelled predicted abundance of individuals occupying areas >1km from coast	(Clemens et al. in prep)	0.1 degree	monthly
Total stream flow	total of coarse interpolation of flow data from gauging stations https://data.gov.au/dataset/water-data-on-line , averaged from spring months at national scale, and annually at regional scale	derived from BOM data	point locations	daily
Surface wetness	modelled predicted upper soil moisture / surface moisture http://www.csiro.au/awap/ averaged from spring months at national scale, and annually at regional scale	CSIRO AWAP	5km	monthly averages
Two year wetness difference	cumulative moisture of last 2 years subtracted from previous 2 years	derived from CSIRO AWAP	5km	monthly averages
Maximum temperature	average daily temperature as measured, interpolated spatially http://www.bom.gov.au/climate/averages/climatology/gridded-data-info/gridded-climate-data.shtml , totalled spatially then averaged from spring months at national scale, and annually at regional scale	BOM	2.5 km	daily

Table S2 Juvenile ratio data from Corner Inlet, the Western Treatment Plant and Western Port. (See also: Minton, C., Jessop, R., and Hassell, C. (2009) Wader breeding success in the 2008 Arctic summer, based on juvenile ratios of birds which spend the non-breeding season in Australia. Arctic Birds. Newsletter of International Breeding Conditions Survey 11, 58-62).

yr_seas	Curlew Sandpiper			Red-necked Stint			Sharp-tailed Sandpiper	
	Western Treatment Plant juvenile ratio	Corner Inlet juvenile ratio	Western Port juvenile ratio	Western Treatment Plant juvenile ratio	Corner Inlet juvenile ratio	Western Port juvenile ratio	Western Treatment Plant juvenile ratio	Western Port juvenile ratio
1982	0.05	0.02	0.09	0.12	0.20	0.26	0.05	NA
1983	0.09	NA	0.32	0.05	0.38	0.04	0.02	0.04
1984	0.03	NA	0.14	0.02	NA	0.10	0.04	0.00
1985	0.03	NA	0.07	0.12	NA	0.34	0.00	0.17
1986	0.03	NA	0.18	0.09	NA	0.25	0.00	NA
1987	0.03	NA	0.05	0.00	NA	0.01	0.04	NA
1988	0.08	NA	0.21	0.17	NA	0.35	0.03	0.15
1989	0.33	0.53	0.56	0.12	0.17	0.09	0.02	NA
1990	0.00	NA	0.01	0.01	NA	0.02	0.00	2.80
1991	0.10	NA	0.12	0.14	NA	0.36	0.12	0.00
1992	0.33	NA	1.13	0.28	NA	0.50	0.16	0.17
1993	0.00	NA	0.00	0.02	NA	0.06	0.00	0.00
1994	0.03	0.00	0.18	0.11	0.02	0.28	0.05	0.00
1995	NA	NA	0.05	0.12	NA	0.43	0.00	0.53
1996	NA	0.13	0.11	NA	0.54	0.40	NA	NA
1997	0.04	0.11	0.13	0.11	0.16	0.23	0.05	0.15
1998	0.45	0.13	0.26	0.09	0.06	0.10	0.33	0.07
1999	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.17	0.27	0.60	0.12	NA
2000	0.08	NA	0.29	0.16	NA	0.17	0.15	0.06
2001	0.07	NA	0.13	0.08	NA	0.23	0.25	NA
2002	0.20	0.06	0.63	0.18	0.45	0.86	0.08	0.00
2003	0.22	0.13	0.12	0.09	NA	0.08	0.14	0.43
2004	0.21	NA	0.10	0.32	NA	0.14	0.82	0.43
2005	0.69	0.40	0.14	0.20	NA	0.06	1.02	0.53
2006	0.61	0.84	0.27	0.06	0.11	0.07	0.37	NA
2007	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.24	0.26	0.12	0.14
2008	0.64	4.50	0.40	0.10	0.03	0.11	0.17	0.00
2009	0.02	0.24	0.13	0.07	1.28	0.18	0.06	0.01
2010	0.12	NA	NA	0.14	0.00	0.13	0.48	NA
2011	NA	NA	NA	0.27	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table S3 Maximum likelihood estimates of apparent annual survival (Φ) for the interval ($t-1$ to t where $t = \text{year}$) and capture probability (P) for three species of migratory shorebird which visit the Western Treatment Plant (a), Western Port (b), or Corner Inlet (c), Victoria, Australia during the nonbreeding season where p_n is the n^{th} percentile of the posterior distribution of survival estimates.

(a)

year	Curlew Sandpiper					Red-necked Stint					Sharp-tailed Sandpiper				
	mean Φ	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Φ	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Φ	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P
Western Treatment Plant															
1982	0.50	0.16	0.26	0.89	0.03	0.62	0.06	0.51	0.74	0.09	0.05	0.10	0.00	0.34	0.09
1983	0.66	0.15	0.38	0.95	0.07	0.62	0.06	0.51	0.74	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.01	0.43	0.09
1984	0.85	0.10	0.64	0.99	0.05	0.86	0.08	0.68	0.99	0.03	0.38	0.22	0.09	0.90	0.03
1985	0.74	0.14	0.47	0.97	0.00	0.89	0.07	0.75	1.00	0.04	0.42	0.23	0.09	0.92	0.04
1986	0.70	0.15	0.44	0.98	0.06	0.45	0.04	0.38	0.54	0.06	0.77	0.17	0.37	0.99	0.06
1987	0.74	0.11	0.54	0.95	0.11	0.72	0.06	0.60	0.84	0.12	0.73	0.19	0.31	0.99	0.12
1988	0.81	0.11	0.59	0.99	0.03	0.81	0.05	0.72	0.92	0.17	0.69	0.20	0.26	0.99	0.17
1989	0.69	0.12	0.46	0.93	0.02	0.84	0.05	0.76	0.93	0.11	0.46	0.25	0.09	0.95	0.11
1990	0.77	0.14	0.49	0.98	0.03	0.64	0.04	0.56	0.71	0.07	0.36	0.25	0.06	0.94	0.07
1991	0.64	0.13	0.43	0.92	0.17	0.77	0.05	0.68	0.87	0.20	0.57	0.25	0.12	0.98	0.20
1992	0.72	0.13	0.48	0.95	0.04	0.67	0.06	0.56	0.78	0.04	0.19	0.18	0.03	0.74	0.04
1993	0.65	0.16	0.37	0.96	0.05	0.66	0.06	0.56	0.77	0.17	0.16	0.18	0.01	0.74	0.17
1994	0.71	0.15	0.44	0.96	0.08	0.82	0.06	0.70	0.95	0.24	0.42	0.27	0.03	0.96	0.24
1995	0.62	0.18	0.32	0.97	0.00	0.75	0.11	0.58	0.98	0.10	0.42	0.25	0.07	0.95	0.10
1996	0.74	0.17	0.39	0.99	0.00	0.39	0.17	0.20	0.77	0.00	0.57	0.25	0.11	0.98	0.00
1997	0.80	0.14	0.47	0.99	0.12	0.63	0.23	0.26	0.98	0.09	0.66	0.23	0.18	0.99	0.09
1998	0.88	0.09	0.66	1.00	0.02	0.68	0.07	0.56	0.83	0.11	0.20	0.20	0.02	0.79	0.11
1999	0.80	0.13	0.53	0.99	0.05	0.85	0.08	0.69	0.98	0.08	0.81	0.15	0.45	0.99	0.08
2000	0.40	0.10	0.25	0.64	0.13	0.75	0.09	0.60	0.94	0.05	0.19	0.09	0.06	0.43	0.05
2001	0.73	0.15	0.44	0.97	0.09	0.57	0.05	0.47	0.68	0.16	0.60	0.19	0.26	0.96	0.16
2002	0.76	0.16	0.42	0.99	0.06	0.72	0.05	0.63	0.81	0.18	0.79	0.16	0.43	0.99	0.18
2003	0.51	0.22	0.15	0.97	0.09	0.81	0.07	0.69	0.96	0.08	0.84	0.12	0.56	1.00	0.08
2004	0.41	0.21	0.13	0.90	0.04	0.77	0.07	0.64	0.91	0.14	0.89	0.10	0.64	1.00	0.14
2005	0.65	0.20	0.27	0.98	0.01	0.74	0.10	0.57	0.97	0.02	0.48	0.20	0.17	0.93	0.02
2006	0.71	0.19	0.30	0.99	0.04	0.52	0.07	0.39	0.65	0.08	0.56	0.22	0.18	0.97	0.08
2007	0.77	0.17	0.36	0.99	0.05	0.82	0.07	0.68	0.95	0.13	0.38	0.24	0.06	0.93	0.13
2008	0.59	0.22	0.20	0.97	0.01	0.61	0.07	0.47	0.74	0.07	0.30	0.22	0.04	0.86	0.07
2009	0.59	0.23	0.17	0.97	0.07	0.65	0.07	0.53	0.82	0.12	0.58	0.24	0.13	0.98	0.12
2010	0.39	0.25	0.07	0.93	0.25	0.88	0.08	0.70	0.99	0.07	0.41	0.27	0.03	0.95	0.07
2011	0.18	0.21	0.01	0.82	0.12	0.91	0.07	0.76	1.00	0.04	0.09	0.15	0.00	0.58	0.04
Average	0.66	0.16	0.37	0.95	0.06	0.71	0.07	0.58	0.86	0.10	0.47	0.20	0.16	0.87	0.10

(b)

year	Curlew Sandpiper					Red-necked Stint					Sharp-tailed Sandpiper				
	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P
Western Port															
1982	0.33	0.08	0.20	0.51	0.08	0.83	0.05	0.73	0.93	0.24	0.21	0.22	0.00	0.84	0.34
1983	0.93	0.06	0.79	1.00	0.16	0.73	0.05	0.64	0.83	0.23	0.36	0.27	0.01	0.94	0.39
1984	0.62	0.06	0.51	0.74	0.10	0.69	0.04	0.61	0.77	0.27	0.40	0.26	0.05	0.96	0.04
1985	0.86	0.08	0.71	0.99	0.17	0.82	0.05	0.72	0.91	0.20	0.60	0.24	0.15	0.98	0.04
1986	0.63	0.07	0.49	0.76	0.17	0.68	0.04	0.61	0.76	0.18	0.52	0.25	0.10	0.96	0.04
1987	0.70	0.06	0.60	0.81	0.06	0.70	0.03	0.64	0.76	0.43	0.62	0.23	0.16	0.98	0.18
1988	0.82	0.06	0.72	0.92	0.10	0.65	0.03	0.60	0.70	0.38	0.28	0.19	0.05	0.82	0.23
1989	0.77	0.06	0.67	0.88	0.18	0.72	0.03	0.66	0.78	0.41	0.43	0.24	0.08	0.94	0.12
1990	0.95	0.04	0.87	1.00	0.07	0.71	0.04	0.63	0.79	0.23	0.80	0.15	0.47	0.99	0.01
1991	0.63	0.07	0.51	0.78	0.10	0.80	0.06	0.67	0.92	0.26	0.48	0.23	0.14	0.96	0.03
1992	0.64	0.08	0.53	0.86	0.03	0.65	0.04	0.58	0.74	0.21	0.51	0.24	0.13	0.96	0.37
1993	0.91	0.06	0.80	1.00	0.16	0.91	0.05	0.81	0.99	0.27	0.18	0.19	0.02	0.80	0.36
1994	0.65	0.05	0.58	0.75	0.09	0.59	0.05	0.52	0.71	0.29	0.07	0.14	0.00	0.55	0.30
1995	0.86	0.09	0.64	0.98	0.10	0.87	0.08	0.68	0.98	0.03	0.36	0.26	0.03	0.94	0.38
1996	0.75	0.11	0.55	0.94	0.02	0.47	0.07	0.37	0.61	0.08	0.35	0.24	0.05	0.91	0.05
1997	0.75	0.15	0.49	0.97	0.02	0.72	0.07	0.58	0.85	0.10	0.53	0.26	0.09	0.97	0.09
1998	0.71	0.11	0.52	0.92	0.05	0.68	0.05	0.59	0.78	0.14	0.30	0.22	0.04	0.85	0.43
1999	0.65	0.09	0.48	0.82	0.06	0.70	0.03	0.63	0.77	0.29	0.40	0.23	0.07	0.91	0.02
2000	0.67	0.11	0.47	0.85	0.14	0.76	0.03	0.69	0.81	0.23	0.46	0.26	0.07	0.95	0.25
2001	0.77	0.09	0.59	0.96	0.04	0.71	0.04	0.64	0.78	0.21	0.34	0.22	0.06	0.88	0.04
2002	0.88	0.08	0.68	1.00	0.02	0.75	0.05	0.66	0.85	0.09	0.58	0.25	0.11	0.98	0.07
2003	0.38	0.06	0.27	0.51	0.10	0.58	0.03	0.52	0.64	0.15	0.47	0.25	0.09	0.96	0.28
2004	0.79	0.08	0.66	0.96	0.09	0.68	0.04	0.60	0.76	0.19	0.28	0.12	0.11	0.58	0.27
2005	0.82	0.13	0.56	0.99	0.04	0.91	0.04	0.82	0.97	0.17	0.59	0.20	0.24	0.97	0.28
2006	0.83	0.13	0.58	0.99	0.11	0.43	0.02	0.40	0.48	0.25	0.19	0.17	0.03	0.67	0.02
2007	0.57	0.16	0.33	0.87	0.00	0.61	0.04	0.54	0.69	0.13	0.51	0.27	0.08	0.97	0.09
2008	0.68	0.22	0.34	0.99	0.07	0.90	0.07	0.72	0.99	0.16	0.63	0.23	0.19	0.98	0.05
2009	0.81	0.16	0.48	0.99	0.02	0.95	0.04	0.85	1.00	0.03	0.48	0.23	0.12	0.95	0.53
2010	0.79	0.14	0.50	0.99	0.01	0.92	0.06	0.78	1.00	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.14	0.36
2011	0.91	0.07	0.75	1.00	0.07	0.97	0.03	0.89	1.00	0.02	0.42	0.29	0.01	0.96	0.46
Average	0.74	0.09	0.56	0.89	0.08	0.74	0.05	0.65	0.82	0.20	0.41	0.22	0.09	0.88	0.20

(c)

year	Curlew Sandpiper					Red-necked Stint					Sharp-tailed Sandpiper				
	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P	mean Phi	sd	p 0.025	p 0.975	P
Comer Inlet															
1982	0.53	0.26	0.10	0.98	0.18	0.45	0.23	0.07	0.92	0.06					
1983	0.16	0.17	0.01	0.72	0.15	0.63	0.21	0.22	0.98	0.00					
1984	0.49	0.28	0.05	0.97	0.23	0.81	0.17	0.39	1.00	0.00	insufficient data				
1985	0.61	0.25	0.10	0.98	0.27	0.86	0.11	0.60	0.99	0.00					
1986	0.64	0.24	0.14	0.98	0.30	0.84	0.14	0.46	0.99	0.04					
1987	0.37	0.25	0.04	0.95	0.18	0.24	0.28	0.02	0.93	0.01					
1988	0.56	0.27	0.08	0.97	0.24	0.46	0.28	0.04	0.97	0.02					
1989	0.63	0.25	0.13	0.99	0.27	0.62	0.25	0.09	0.98	0.30					
1990	0.17	0.17	0.02	0.64	0.43	0.60	0.15	0.38	0.93	0.00					
1991	0.64	0.23	0.17	0.98	0.06	0.77	0.16	0.46	0.99	0.02					
1992	0.65	0.23	0.16	0.98	0.06	0.96	0.04	0.86	1.00	0.03					
1993	0.59	0.21	0.27	0.97	0.01	0.45	0.10	0.30	0.66	0.04					
1994	0.80	0.15	0.45	0.99	0.03	0.79	0.15	0.49	1.00	0.02					
1995	0.69	0.19	0.33	0.99	0.01	0.77	0.15	0.47	0.99	0.00					
1996	0.74	0.17	0.38	0.98	0.04	0.73	0.14	0.50	0.99	0.02					
1997	0.64	0.21	0.23	0.98	0.01	0.86	0.11	0.64	1.00	0.01					
1998	0.80	0.15	0.46	0.99	0.17	0.82	0.12	0.56	1.00	0.04					
1999	0.75	0.18	0.38	0.99	0.04	0.38	0.08	0.26	0.55	0.02					
2000	0.72	0.19	0.31	0.99	0.02	0.77	0.13	0.51	0.98	0.03					
2001	0.19	0.15	0.04	0.67	0.01	0.82	0.12	0.60	1.00	0.02					
2002	0.55	0.25	0.14	0.98	0.05	0.82	0.11	0.57	0.98	0.01					
2003	0.49	0.24	0.09	0.95	0.15	0.48	0.08	0.35	0.64	0.00					
2004	0.44	0.25	0.07	0.94	0.07	0.91	0.08	0.71	1.00	0.00					
2005	0.60	0.26	0.13	0.99	0.12	0.94	0.05	0.81	1.00	0.01					
2006	0.55	0.25	0.12	0.98	0.23	0.21	0.03	0.15	0.28	0.11					
2007	0.22	0.22	0.01	0.86	0.33	0.78	0.13	0.50	0.99	0.10					
2008	0.21	0.22	0.01	0.87	0.09	0.74	0.13	0.48	0.99	0.00					
2009	0.30	0.26	0.02	0.93	0.35	0.75	0.15	0.45	0.99	0.02					
2010	0.10	0.15	0.00	0.61	0.36	0.22	0.18	0.03	0.64	0.01					
2011	0.42	0.29	0.01	0.97	0.46	0.27	0.20	0.03	0.77	0.01					
Average	0.51	0.22	0.15	0.93	0.16	0.66	0.14	0.40	0.90	0.03					

Table S4 Shorebird count data from Corner Inlet, the Western Treatment Plant and Western Port.

Year	Curlew Sandpiper			Red-necked Stint			Sharp-tailed Sandpiper		
	Corner Inlet count	Western Treatment Plant count	Western Port average roost count	Corner Inlet count	Western Treatment Plant count	Western Port average roost count	Corner Inlet count	Western Treatment Plant count	Western Port average roost count
1982	3700	4459	303	11970	9389	473	222	6052	10
1983	5200	13323	309	10917	4801	374	300	2687	28
1984	2800	7981	331	9720	6190	438	1	2084	8
1985	1600	4195	169	12550	6860	292	50	2684	8
1986	2690	6752	356	13000	7744	259	50	4336	23
1987	1480	2891	397	7570	4463	302	3	5125	38
1988	2160	2543	355	6320	3045	473	101	3405	108
1989	1400	8450	439	7370	10202	568	200	5037	90
1990	2400	2941	577	7700	5684	333	51	0	204
1991	2620	3481	299	9270	3408	439	60	2685	29
1992	5740	6975	399	9250	5429	719	100	3078	29
1993	2171	1376	343	7665	4841	782	60	1281	6
1994	2900	4163	411	12500	7063	358	178	3898	46
1995	1580	2201	561	14300	4315	473	10	3106	47
1996	1060	3329	641	12050	7504	367	3	3002	5
1997	1005	2351	195	10005	8706	520	50	4060	3
1998	550	2869	383	8800	7753	472	100	3843	23
1999	828	4299	409	14200	7178	530	2	3661	23
2000	920	5074	NA	23675	5603	NA	80	2714	NA
2001	781	825	NA	21420	6547	NA	15	850	NA
2002	600	1404	275	15800	8895	821	0	2894	37
2003	550	1453	62	13500	13642	333	5	2456	21
2004	102	2226	114	16210	7555	592	0	2198	25
2005	300	818	250	12049	10246	699	150	7158	17
2006	400	2796	31	8100	8322	544	160	4089	21
2007	534	2274	55	7135	11031	321	12	3725	19
2008	670	3051	NA	10700	7144	NA	27	3449	NA
2009	250	1119	100	12550	7900	563	25	2884	7
2010	65	921	26	9250	5608	238	50	2730	3
2011	30	1064	NA	13260	5441	NA	0	10	NA

S5 Figures showing selected univariate relationships in variables used in multivariate testing.

Figure S5a. Average Curlew Sandpiper apparent survival at three locations plotted against maximum temperature averaged by grid cell within 500 kilometers of the study sites.

Figure S5b. Average Curlew Sandpiper apparent survival at three locations plotted against totalled predicted abundance within the whole of inland Australia.

Curlew Sandpiper

Figure S5c. Average Curlew Sandpiper juvenile ratio at three locations plotted against totalled stream flow (centred) per grid cell within the whole of inland Australia.

Figure S5d. Average Sharp-tailed Sandpiper count at three locations plotted against totalled stream flow (centred) per grid cell within the whole of inland Australia.